

THE ROLE OF COLLOQUIAL AND VERNACULAR VOCABULARY IN THE LANGUAGE OF FICTION

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Abstract. *Colloquial and prosaic vocabulary in the language of modern writers is a frequent phenomenon. The aim of this article is to find out the peculiarities of colloquial and vernacular vocabulary usage in the language of modern writers.*

Key words: *vocabulary, modernity, linguistics, lexical borrowing, expressiveness, literary text, metaphoricity.*

РОЛЬ РАЗГОВОРНОЙ И ПРОСТОРЕЧНОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ НА ЯЗЫКЕ ФАНТАСТИКИ

Аннотация. *Разговорно-прозаическая лексика в языке современных писателей — частое явление. Цель данной статьи - выявить особенности употребления разговорной и просторечной лексики в языке современных писателей.*

Ключевые слова: *лексика, современность, языкознание, лексическое заимствование, экспрессивность, художественный текст, метафоричность.*

INTRODUCTION

Colloquial and colloquial words in the language of works of fiction are not uncommon. The main emphasis we see in the movement of lexical units-elements from the deep spheres of language to the center of the system. Such units include jargon, colloquial vocabulary, and colloquialisms.

It must be said that these are the words that give expressiveness to the text. In the modern media: newspapers and magazines are expressive notes in the sections "News", there is a large number of colloquial and vernacular words, which gives the text a certain criticism, irony or harshness (if it is about topical events). It is through the use of stylistically colored words that the reader most clearly and clearly represents the position of the author.

Vocabulary of oral speech is heterogeneous and is divided into two large groups:

- 1) Colloquial vocabulary;
- 2) Prostoric vocabulary.

The colloquial vocabulary includes words that give the speech a peculiar shade of casualness, informality. For example: nonsense, in a friendly way, shoddy, bai, ouch.

The colloquial vocabulary does not go beyond the limits of the Russian literary language. The colloquial vocabulary, however, is "lower" in style than the colloquial one, so it is outside the strictly normative Russian literary speech.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

An important task of journalism is to convince the reader in the clarity and correctness of the author's position, that it is necessary to solve the problem shown in the text as soon as possible. This requires the publicist to be able to convince, to understand the psychology and worldview of the reader. In addition, the author presents the problem, based on reliable information, therefore, he needs to know the history of the issue, the ability to analyze the steps already taken in solving the situation, the understanding of the real possibilities to change something for the better.

The use in this genre of colloquial, colloquial and jargon vocabulary is possible, as it is this approach, characterizes the personality of the author, and actively forms the attitude to the described event, phenomenon, fact. The metaphorical language of the above vocabulary wants to hide everything and say everything at the same time.

However, it should be remembered that emotions and expression in jargonisms are rare: there are almost always two main lines - positive and negative. This limits the use of jargonisms in fiction, but as for journalism, they are allowed. In order to make the text expressive, the publicist enhances the impact on the reader in various "ways", including slang words. And in the epistolary genre, in order to explain his point of view on the event being described, the very two emotional characteristics - positive and negative - are quite sufficient.

Thus, many words pass the way from jargon - to prosaic, entering into wide use. Prostaretsiye include words peculiar to the speech of the population with a low cultural level, words that do not belong to the literary norm. The colloquial words are included in journalism as common for understanding, carrying a sharp evaluative and stylistic coloring: bald, cool, mess (disorder), cash (cash), bucks and many others. After all, these are mostly jargonisms that are firmly entrenched in colloquial vernacular. They can also be found in the modern press, especially in youth publications.

Unfortunately, day by day publicist and fiction texts are more and more filled with colloquial words, thereby replacing the literary language.

The interest of linguists in the colloquial and vernacular vocabulary is enormous. This can be explained not only by the poorly studied vocabulary of the vernacular, but also by the diverse role played by the vernaculars and colloquial words in the development of the Russian language as a whole: the vernacular vocabulary is one of the permanent components of spoken language, giving it emotionality and expressiveness. Prostoreal vocabulary is one of the important branches of the language of works of fiction.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Proverbial words are characteristic of colloquial speech. As noted above, they serve as characteristics of the phenomenon in the circle of everyday relations; they do not go out of the norms of literary word usage, but give the speech a relaxedness. Prostoroye is characteristic of non-literary urban colloquial speech, which contains many recent dialect words, words of colloquial origin, new formations arising to characterize a variety of everyday phenomena, word-forming variants of neutral vocabulary. Proverbial word is used in the literary language as a stylistic tool to give the speech a touch of humorous, disparaging, ironic, rude, etc. Often these words are expressive, expressive synonyms of words of neutral vocabulary.

So, the connection between literary language and colloquial speech is very strong. More precisely, colloquial speech is part of the literary language. The changes that occur in language are a product of the development of society, its spiritual and material culture, science and technology. Replenishment of the vocabulary of the literary language is carried out by the transition of colloquial, vernacular words in written language. Cases of such transition can take place in the works of writers and poets.

The use of specific words in the works of literary style is due to the desire to increase the imagery of the text. Moreover, by motives of stylistic expediency, for example for the verbal characteristics of characters, masters of the word introduce dialectal words, colloquial vocabulary, create neologisms, original turns of speech, etc. into the fabric of a literary work.

And it is thanks to the abundance of colloquial words in the speech of the hero, the reader can more fully imagine not only his character, but even his social status, etc. In short, what is considered unacceptable in general linguistic use, in fiction can be used as a means of high expressiveness.

DISCUSSION

Note that the use of colloquial words in works of this kind is primarily due to the author's position, and in no way can be interpreted as a violation of the stylistics of works. However, it is in this way in the literary language may consolidate some colloquial norms, turning into literary. Prostatic language in comparison with colloquial language is more coarse and its use is characteristic of a certain layer of modern society. Note that the words belonging to the vernacular language can very often have a negative coloring. The degree of negative stylistic coloring of a word can affect the general perception of the speaker's speech (or written text).

Proverbs are divided into non-literary and literary words. Non-literary words are a very specific part of the Russian language. Most often their use is typical for some closed social groups with a low level of education, weak notions and moral and ethical norms and requirements of the society in which they live. A particularly striking example is the use of such non-literary vernaculars as jargons.

It should be noted that the mechanisms of interaction between the literary language and extra-literary spheres of speech cannot be considered fully understood. In this connection, of considerable interest is the picture of assimilation by colloquial speech and literary vernaculars of elements coming from various social dialects, professional vernaculars, slang vocabulary, youth slang, etc.

Literary language, and especially the journalistic style, is constantly replenished at the expense of dialect, vernacular and slang lexicon, which comes into common use, as a rule, in modified form and usually having lost the semantic connection with its source of origin and specific occurrence. Mutual influence and interpenetration characterize in general the social dialects and the relations between them. The words of one jargon can easily pass into another. This predetermines the complex nature of interaction between the literary language and social dialects (or social varieties of speech).

CONCLUSION

Living forms of language (colloquial speech, dialectal speech, literary popular speech, everyday speech, etc.), opposing the literary language within the unified national language as the leading variety of this language, in a literary text are also close to the units of literary language, since they both perform a single function - aesthetic, on the one hand, and style-forming, on the other. The style of the fiction text, the style of the writer, the style of the literary work is an inseparable unity of components, inadequate elements of the system of literary language. Thus, we have considered the process of interaction between colloquial speech and literary language. However, the picture of these interactions cannot be complete without a detailed analysis of the main features of colloquial speech and literary-written language and comparison of their differences.

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